

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY

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ISSUES OF FOREIGN MIGRATION IN THE POLICY OF THE GOVERNMENT OF UZBEKISTAN AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE MIDDLE CLASS

Dusov Qobil Ochilovich

under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

State Administration Academy

Doctoral student of the Department of "Management Sociology and Psychology".

krestof1984@mail.ru

Abstract: This article analyzes the foreign migration policy of the government of Uzbekistan and its impact on the development of the middle class. The article examines the dynamics of migration flows, the socio-economic status of labor migrants and their role in the formation of the middle class. Based on the results of the research, proposals were made to increase the positive impact of foreign migration on the economy of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: external migration, middle class, labor migrants, remittances, migration policy, economic development

INTRODUCTION

At the current time, when the processes of globalization are intensifying, external migration is becoming an urgent issue for many countries, including Uzbekistan. In particular, the increase in the scale of labor migration from our

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country to foreign countries and its socio-economic consequences attract the attention of the society. This article analyzes the policy of the government of Uzbekistan on foreign migration and its impact on the development of the middle class.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

During the research, the official data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations and the Central Bank were used. Scientific literature and experts' opinions on the subject were also analyzed.

Statistical analysis, comparative analysis and expert evaluation methods were used as research methods.

RESULTS

The main destinations of foreign labor migration from Uzbekistan are Russia, Kazakhstan, Turkey and South Korea. According to official data, the number of Uzbek citizens working abroad in 2022 was 1.9 million [1].

Table 1. Dynamics of labor migration from Uzbekistan to the main countries (thousands of people)

Country	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Russia	1500	1640	1150	1410	1550
Kazakhstan	180	210	150	190	220
Turkey	50	65	45	60	80
J. Korea	25	30	20	28	35
Others	10	15	8	12	15
Total	1765	1960	1373	1700	1900

Source: Information from the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan

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Remittances of labor migrants are important for the economy of Uzbekistan. According to the data of the Central Bank, in 2022, the volume of cross-border money transfers made by individuals amounted to 14.5 billion US dollars [2].

DISCUSSION

Foreign labor migration in Uzbekistan and its impact on the development of the middle class is a complex and multifaceted process. In recent years, this issue has gained not only economic, but also social and political importance. The results of the analysis show that labor migration has a significant impact on the economy and society of Uzbekistan, especially in terms of the formation and development of the middle class.

First, remittances of labor migrants serve as an important financial source for the country's economy. The amount of remittances to Uzbekistan in 2022 amounted to 14.5 billion US dollars is a clear proof of our opinion. These funds serve to increase family incomes, improve living standards, and stimulate consumer demand. As a result, many families are able to move up to the middle class level. For example, due to remittances, families are getting middle-class opportunities such as improving housing conditions, buying cars, and educating their children in quality educational institutions.

Second, the experience of working abroad improves the professional qualifications and skills of labor migrants. They are getting an opportunity to get acquainted with modern technologies, work methods and management practices. This, in turn, helps to increase competitiveness in the labor market after returning home and to occupy high-paying jobs. For example, after returning to Uzbekistan, migrants who worked in the construction industry in Russia open small construction companies and become representatives of the middle class.

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Thirdly, the financial resources and experience gained as a result of labor migration create great opportunities for the development of entrepreneurial activities. Many migrant workers return home with enough capital and knowledge to start their own businesses. This leads to the development of small and medium-sized businesses, which are the mainstay of the middle class. For example, in South Korea, modern greenhouses, car service centers and small manufacturing enterprises opened by migrants returning from work can be a clear example of this.

Fourth, while working abroad, migrant workers gain new social and cultural experience. They are getting to know different cultures, values and ways of life. This broadens their worldview and forms characteristics such as openness, tolerance and innovative thinking characteristic of the modern middle class. As a result, they become a force that actively participates in social and political processes in the society and contributes to the development of civil society.

Fifth, as a result of labor migration, new opportunities for foreign investments are emerging in Uzbekistan. Migrants who have gained experience working abroad are playing an important role in attracting foreign investors to Uzbekistan using their connections. This contributes to the creation of new jobs, technology transfer and economic growth in the country. For example, textile factories or food enterprises opened through the mediation of Uzbek migrants who worked in Turkey can serve as an example.

However, the negative effects of foreign labor migration on the society and economy of Uzbekistan should not be ignored. First of all, there is the problem of "brain drain". The departure of highly qualified specialists, scientists, engineers and other professions abroad is a serious loss for the country. This may negatively affect the innovative development and competitiveness of Uzbekistan in the long term.

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Secondly, the division of families and social problems are occurring. Many men are away from their families for long periods of time, leading to the breakdown of family relationships, problems in raising children, and even divorce. This has a negative impact on the institution of the family, which is the main link of society.

Thirdly, there is a problem of insufficient provision of social protection among labor migrants. As many migrants work in the informal sector, they are deprived of rights such as social security, health insurance and pensions. This creates a risk of them becoming a layer in need of social protection in the future.

Fourthly, as a result of labor migration, there is a shortage of labor resources in some regions. Especially in rural areas, there is a labor shortage in agriculture and other fields as a result of the emigration of young and able-bodied people. This hinders the development of some sectors of the country's economy.

Fifth, there is the risk of dependence on remittances. Although remittances are important for the economy of Uzbekistan, this situation makes the country overly dependent on external economic factors. For example, in 2020, the sharp decline in remittances due to the COVID-19 pandemic had a negative impact on the well-being of many families.

At this point, it is necessary to pay attention to the policy of the government of Uzbekistan in the field of foreign labor migration. In recent years, a number of important steps have been taken in this regard. In particular, the Law "On Foreign Labor Migration" adopted in 2020 created an important legal basis for protecting the rights and interests of labor migrants and providing them with social support. Also, the Foreign Labor Migration Agency was established under the Ministry of Employment and Labor Relations, through which systematic work was launched to help labor migrants find employment abroad and protect their rights.

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In addition, the government is implementing vocational training and retraining programs for labor migrants. Through these programs, migrants are given the necessary skills to be competitive and earn high wages abroad. At the same time, a number of measures are being implemented to provide employment to labor migrants who have returned to their homeland, and to support their entrepreneurial initiatives. For example, incentive mechanisms such as providing preferential loans and tax breaks to returning migrants have been introduced.

In short, foreign labor migration has a significant impact on the formation and development of the middle class in Uzbekistan. This process serves economic growth, population welfare and social development. However, the negative consequences should not be ignored. Therefore, it is important to further improve the migration policy carried out by the government, to strengthen the mechanisms for protecting the rights and interests of labor migrants, to ensure their social protection and to continue efforts to improve their skills. Only then will it be possible to maximize the positive effects of foreign labor migration and reduce its negative consequences.

In the future, the government of Uzbekistan should pay special attention to the following directions in the field of foreign labor migration:

1. Increasing the legal literacy of labor migrants. For this, it is necessary to conduct large-scale information campaigns and strengthen the activity of legal consultation centers. Through this, migrants can better understand and protect their rights.

2. Expansion of cooperation with foreign countries in the field of labor migration. It is necessary to strengthen the legal status of migrants through bilateral agreements, and to improve mechanisms for ensuring their social protection.

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3. Expansion of training programs for labor migrants. This not only increases their competitiveness abroad, but also increases their chances of finding a job as a highly qualified specialist when they return home.

4. Strengthen programs to provide employment to returning migrants and support their entrepreneurial initiatives. Through this, their knowledge and experience can be effectively directed for the development of the country's economy.

5. To encourage remittances to be invested. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop special investment programs and improve mechanisms for providing preferential loans.

6. Development of programs for repatriation and attraction of highly qualified specialists to solve the problem of "brain drain". By offering them decent working conditions and competitive salaries, the innovative potential of the country can be increased.

7. Improving the system of social support for families of labor migrants. This is especially important in terms of raising and educating children, maintaining family relationships.

8. To expand the use of modern information technologies for management and analysis of migration processes. This will make it possible to forecast and effectively manage migration flows.

CONCLUSION

Thus, external labor migration remains an important factor in the formation and development of the middle class in Uzbekistan. By properly managing and directing this process, a great contribution can be made to the economic and social development of the country. This requires constant improvement of state policy, study of international experience and adaptation to national conditions, as well as

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close cooperation with civil society institutions. In this way, Uzbekistan can maximize the positive effect of foreign labor migration and reduce its negative consequences. This, in turn, leads to the formation of a stable and prosperous middle class in the country, economic growth and social stability.

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